

REFLECTION ON THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ON THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7916623

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*Pedagogue. Postdoctoral in Psychology. Athena Educational Institute. Scientific consultant.
srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.*

Liliane Rodrigues de Araújo

*Master in Education. Pedagogue at the State Department of Education of Espírito Santo –
SEDU (ES). liliaraujoe10@hotmail.com.*

Raquel Rodrigues Teles

*Graduated in Languages-Portuguese (UFES). Portuguese Language and Writing and
Expression Teacher at Rede Alternativo de Ensino - Serra (ES) raquelrodt@gmail.com.*

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of the impact of digital technology on the educational environment. It should be noted that its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it analyzes how the implementation of information and communication technologies impacted the teaching-learning relationship. Its social relevance stands out in the aspect of promoting clarification about the possibilities of use and advances of digital technologies as a way of bringing together the possibilities of teaching and learning. It is a bibliographical, factual, analytical research, based on authors who study and discuss, academically, this problem. The objective is to present a discursive analysis involving the theme in order to expand the potentialities regarding the use of modern information and communication technologies in educational environments. It is concluded that when using Information and Communication Technologies in education as a search for a space of creation and as a connection space between the known and the unknown, cracks are opened in the security of what has already been thought to let pass the richness of what has not yet been thought of and make it possible to develop learning environments that rescue the dimensionality of cognition through understanding the world as a unit of knowledge.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technologies; Educational Environment; Teaching-learning processes.

INTRODUCTION

Like every technology that comes with the promise of solving all of humanity's problems and others that promise to solve a very wide variety of basic needs, information and communication technologies arrived with a whole discursive apparatus that scared even the most courageous individuals, promising to transform the classroom into an immense multiverse laboratory, where machines and students would be the contextual present reality. The speech was loaded with fantastic, surreal and far-fetched symbolism, preached by philosophers disconnected from the basic formal educational reality, which scared the teachers even more.

The speech proposed that students would be able to learn faster, not because they were super intelligent or would become so, as if by osmotic action caused by contact with the super intelligent machines that would be at their entire disposal; but because the machines would be able to offer them exact answers to their questions in real time and with the clarity of a miraculous genius created by Hollywood. However, there is an urgent need to analyze how technologies came and continue to influence the lives of students and teachers in the most diverse sectors of formal education. Reality is very far from a dialectical relationship between the two, leaving room for speculations of the type as if it were yet another product of capitalist influence with a view to garnering purely mercantilist advantages at the expense of inculcating an untrue proposal, *a siren song contemporary*.

The propagated discourse is that the background and point of departure and arrival of informatization would be the possibility of building a [*more*] democratic society, with more equal participation in knowledge, innovations and wealth. The computerization of society will tend towards one or another dimension, democratizing or oligopolistic, depending on the socio-political scheme of distribution of power and wealth, where the computerization process is immersed.

By using Information and Communication Technologies in education as a search for a space of creation and as a connection space between the known and the unknown, cracks are opened in the security of what has already been thought to let pass the richness of what has not yet been thought of and make possible the dream of learning environments that rescue the dimensionality of cognition through understanding the world as a unit of knowledge. So, instead of the emptiness between disciplines, it can be seen that there is something between and through them and beyond the fact that each and every discipline is full of potential, leaving teachers and students to explore it further (both vertical and horizontal) in investigative,

epistemological, cognitive processes and in carrying out experiments, in order to arrive at theory.

Up to this point, everything seems magical, fantastic; but, it is necessary to be clear that these new tools are just that and nothing more; that is, they are not able to replace the man, the analyst, the well-prepared technician or the dedicated professor, whose praxis is based on logic; because, they are nothing more than means that collaborate so that ends are achieved, they are not ends in and by themselves. In the 20th century, when capitalism reached its highest level and science and the technique of mass production needed new markets, generating a high level of selfishness and competitiveness among industrialized nations, scientific discoveries and inventions were so valued that the notion of man as a pragmatic element was lost.

The split established in the human being, creating a man-idea dichotomy, caused him to lose his inner harmony and inadvertently become a being in crisis. This crisis is expressed in all senses: social, caused by the new order established by the situation (industrialism), in which what matters is production; psychological, as a result of the new focus on valuing man, ceasing to be important for his inner activity, for what he produces in the concrete material plane. The advances in means of communication and transport, although they serve to reduce the physical distance between people, have not been able to increase the degree of solidarity between them.

The emergencies on which modern philosophy reflected were replaced by new concerns centered on science, technology and the problematic of the individual and social human being. The new period manifests a continuity and a rupture with the previous one. Elements of science from the 17th and 18th centuries remain and become explicit, as well as elements of the Enlightenment; however, in another context and with new concerns. Faced with this, the philosophical discourse diversified and took several directions, becoming fragmented and oriented either towards a spiritualist tendency, returning to the interiority of the individual, or towards a practical, utilitarian tendency, linked to human action. Thus, the philosophical experience will vary between an idealist and a materialist posture, originating from them various doctrines such as pragmatism, intuitionism, phenomenology, Marxism, existentialism.

The pragmatic formation of a human being is *a conditio sine qua non* for him to become aware of his social role, not only with his other equals but also as a being responsible for the balance of the other creatures with whom he shares his life. terrestrial space. Proper rationalization, the search for critical knowledge, achieved through experience, that allows you to doubt the entire process that involves it, clarifies and promotes advances is part of humanistic training [*or at least it should be*]. Although,

The division of society, in which people perform delimited and very specific tasks, causes the human quality of work and life to disappear. The person does not see the whole situation, but only sees a small part of the big picture, and so is unable to act without some kind of general direction (MILGRAM, 1983, p. 28)

In the same way that the natives of the Colombian Americas could not mentalize a man mounted on a horse as two distinct units, imagining him as a chimerical creature, simply because he did not know the function of the horse as a mount, so is the modern man who works in the industry automobilist, *eg.*, and who, when seeing a car, cannot completely conceive it in their minds, because they do not know the parts that compose it. And so does formal education at all levels. It continues to be fragmented more and more until the whole process is nothing more than isolated pieces of useless knowledge, generating an unfortunate academic continuation that never materializes into something feasible and pragmatic.

Friedrich Nietzsche (1844-1900), in his *Writings on Education* (2003) reports that, as the man of science wallows in the search for a solution to a single problem, he ends up forgetting and letting go of the whole, and thus, is languishing more and more in its epistemological process. For the common man, even a savage man, who even fears this new insertion, technology is either something that does not exist or he resists it so much that he withdraws into an inner world that causes him to be ostracized on a broad spectrum. For the average man, who was not taught to think or if he was taught in a mediocre way, these advances mean comfort and protection and for him it doesn't make the slightest difference what direction things come to take. He is grateful to God that he had the ability to learn something beyond his primitive capabilities.

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ON THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Taking advantage of an analogy, the technological revolution brought a serious problem for education, which was having to *adapt* to this new reality [*while its pupils were already ahead*] and fight against illiteracy and digital exclusion. The fight was uneven, as it was given three functions and no apparatus, after all, there is no way for the school to engender it in its curriculum if its agents either ignore the new technology or [even] resist it. The technological revolution is still in its infancy in a world that is increasingly concerned with the humanistic formation of the subject and since the school is the product of a culture and a time, it is up to it to seek to overcome this culture, to mold it into a humanistic structure in order to be able to

apply it. it in its entirety. Adds to the problem the fact that no methodology of effective action, in order to face the situation, was proposed or presented to the teachers; they were just told that, from then on, they should include the discipline, the tool and the students in the digital world, as if they were completely aware of everything that was happening, to come and connected to the world wide web and in a network .

The expansion and sophistication of modern scientific information systems are aimed at facilitating contacts, combined with the immense volume of scientific production that tends to be so large today that insurmountable problems of information overload arise for individual scientists. The consequence is that it becomes increasingly difficult for a scientist to keep track of what is happening outside his narrow field of expertise. As a substitute for the integration and coherence of an entire scientific area, what the individual researcher does is follow what happens in the most prestigious centers and in the most prestigious journals, taking them as indicators of where the frontiers are at each moment . of scientific activity, which tends to be true; but not always. The search for an intermediate position between the total subordination of science to technological, economic and political objectives, on the one hand, and the complete independence of science, on the other, has led to attempts to establish rational criteria for the distribution of resources among different types of scientific activity.

Technological development has brought fantastic advances, such as computers, however, they are not magic machines that can guess things that are hidden from people. Wonderful as they are, they are limited to the knowledge that human beings impute to their artificial neuroelectronic systems, that is, computers depend on people to acquire knowledge and, likewise, to express it. Professor Valdemar Setzer (2003) vehemently emphasizes that

Certain human activities cannot be performed by the computer. In my conceptualization, computers will never feel or think like human beings. Therefore, they have limitations that you should be aware of. One must also know the human capabilities, which transcend machines. The great danger is seeing people as machines.

Creating and feeding the illusion that machines are more capable than humans is a naive idea, which is nonetheless bizarre; however, it finds its limitations and finitudes, by itself. However, the danger posed by the professor mentioned above is in considering people neither less nor more than machines, placing them on an equal footing without any judicious evaluation parameter. This would be like carrying out a process of ethical trivialization and letting things flow as the neo-liberalist need understands, completely at the whim of the volatile direction it takes.

The human brain is an optimized structure ready to protect/defend the entire organism from a [*possible*] collapse, making use of the most varied somatic manifestations. And the best-known forms of individual protection are socialization, communication, peaceful coexistence (*sic*) and breaking routines. Condemn people to stagnate in a mechanical, mimetic world and in a *frenzy* of ultra-savage competition, whose ultimate motive is to surpass their colleague, who now presents himself and is recognized as a rival, an enemy to be defeated under any circumstances, it is to machine not only human beings but also social relations.

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES ADDED TO EDUCATIONAL PRAXIS

The technological revolution is a reality; arrived at schools and an interesting fact happens that many times the teacher is totally unprepared for the tasks performed via the network. Being attentive to new changes in the market is the order of the day. The use of technologies in education is already an essential reality and one cannot think of a complete humanistic formation without digital inclusion as an effective part of it. Every living being resists the new; this is because the new is unknown and this condition provokes and enhances fear. And this is what is the cause of resistance. Even the development of human culture and the species itself, had its obstacles, due to this fear, this resistance to accepting the unknown. Finally, this ends up being a defense mechanism. Du Bois (1961) argues that,

The propagation mechanism of techniques is dominated by a strong agent hostile to development, and by the innate tendency of naive people to reproduce, invariably, the forms transmitted by their parents and transmit them, without modifications, to the next generation. In this way, such forms were preserved, completely unchanged from prehistoric times, for millennia, since this innate tendency opposes any change in tradition (DU BOIS, 1961, p. 131 *apud* KATZENSTEIN, 1986, p. 39).

Technological development has brought fantastic advances, such as computers, however, they are not magic machines that can guess things that are hidden from people. Wonderful as they are, they are limited to the knowledge we give them. Computers depend on people to acquire knowledge. The educational process via digital technologies faces a vigorous dilemma that, at first sight, seems to be insoluble. If, on the one hand, it emerges as the quintessence to solve an equation posed by the Lutheran Revolution (1517) that defended a universalized education, on the other hand, the question arises of the unpreparedness of schools to adapt to this new reality. This is because the school is a traditional center, *par excellence*,

which has always taken care of the formation of the individual, his preparation for life, leaving the parents to guide their children towards a certain profession . With the post-war revolutions, these barriers began to overlap, until they culminated in the Federal Constitution of 1988, bringing in its article 205, that the mission of the school is to prepare for life, citizen training and for the labor market, as *in verbis*:

Art. 205. Education, a right of all and a duty of the State and the family, will be promoted and encouraged with the collaboration of society , aiming at the full development of the person, his preparation for the exercise of citizenship and his qualification for work (BRASIL, 1988, p. 17).

Under this new concept of education, information and communication technologies - (ICTs) gain strength due to their broad coverage power and provision of information in real time, leaving it to the teacher [*in situ*] to decode the contents exposed to the students.

The school can add values to media content, such as the interconnection between different cultures and their influences on the subjects involved in the educational process. One cannot fail to foresee that the conduction and production of a new ideology, creating the '*mass media*' may follow a dangerous form of mental alienation. To claim that ICTs have a specificity is to place them as holders and dictators of a power that may end up becoming hegemonic. It would be Orwell's 1984-style creation of a state. And, following this line of ambiguity, it can be said that television, more properly, serves to add the excluded class to the democratic process at once and voice. However, it can also serve as a machine for the State's ideological propagation and an instrument of mass alienation, aiming at the *status quo* of absolute and unrestricted control.

And, according to Habermas (1929-), objective scientific knowledge no longer promotes liberation and enlightenment; rather, it serves as an ideology that supports the *status quo* . This is mainly because, for knowledge to be valid, it has to result from free and open dialogue, which is severely constrained by political and other constraints under capitalism. Education's mission is to equalize 'opportunities', never people. With science, whether technological and/or humanistic, one must look for this right measure, this means that provides balance to the equation, after all, "humanity is not divided into heroes and tyrants. Their passions, good or bad, were given to them by society, not by nature" (CHAPLIN *apud* GOMES, 2007, p. 32).

According to this analysis, technical development and science focused on technical application, which result from this instrumental reason , entail the loss of the autonomy of the good itself, which is also subject to the rules of technical domination of the natural world. Based

on a critical perspective, it is therefore necessary to recover the dimension of human interaction, of a non-instrumental rationality, based on communicative action between free subjects, with an emancipatory character in relation to technical domination. Ideology corresponds, therefore, to Habermas, to the distortion of this possibility of communicative action, producing asymmetrical relations and preventing interaction from fully taking place.

In Brazil, television has faithfully fulfilled its intended role: 'making people give up their [*already obsolete and mediocre*] habit of reading.

Our current managed societies use more subtle and effective expedients: the bombardment of information by the mass media, especially by television complexes, makes censorship and control over minds aseptic. It is not necessary to destroy the books if the generations, without them and the adults being clearly aware of it, are 'dis-taught' of the practice of critical reading (RAMOS-DE-OLIVEIRA, 1997, p. 31).

The country, as a place of great illiteracy and little reading, is a propitious field for the development of an *educational image*'. The image is also a text, a context; imagery is read ; however, the expulsion of the letter by the image suffocates the process of reflection, without which nothing is achieved. During this period, new ethical-pedagogical models were developed. It is noticed that the mass information technology had its project [*subtly*] modified to 'mass alienation technology'. However, one cannot lose sight of the fact that it has served to cross barriers that, before, were not even imagined by our ancestors from times considered highly evolved and classical. And in this new paradigm, where is the teacher? Until proven otherwise, in the same place as always, after all, the human being continues to be a political animal, according to the Aristotelian conception, the *zoon politikon* , in Jaspers' conception, that is, a being that needs the *other* not only to identify oneself as belonging to the genus and species, but to define oneself culturally and socially.

Within this concept, it can be inferred that the human socio-educational activity is inherent to the genre, being essential for a complete learning the presence of attributes such as affectivity, social interaction and a mutual and constant exchange of principles and values.

The television media has created a parallel class in society which are the pseudo-wise [*those who think they know something about anything*]; forming a group that ends up disseminating a derogatory knowledge devoid of the slightest epistemological value. This group was intensified by broadband internet access, in which individual power expands exponentially and without any kind of control.

An impression that television and, finally, the internet have leveraged is that it is equalizing opportunities and thus promoting the insertion of the excluded individual into the

environment, gaining them time and voice. What they really do is enhance even more the process of exclusion and alienation, leading individuals to an attitude of not wanting to fight for an ideal and feeding illusions about furtive and parameterless careers guided by the pseudo idea of large and easy earnings.

literature and critical reading are brought up, it is worth mentioning that both require a frank abstraction process; something that, in solitude, is impossible to achieve. And television production is a monologue that gives the false impression of being a dialogue. It is a questioning that comes ready-made, canned, plastered; ready for use and abuse and it's no use complaining, because they don't listen to you, the guy on this side of the screen is anonymous, trapped in a bitter process of anomie. On the internet, there is a condition of synchronous interaction; however, the individuals that make up the groups that form think the same way, there is no conflict; soon, the discussion becomes innocuous and meaningless, because everyone agrees with everything that the colleague expresses.

According to research by a French philosopher, Gilles Lepovetsky, 98% of the population 'only' watch sex programs and other trivia on TV. An English study proved that children who watch television are at risk of developing 'autism'. This is due to excessive isolation and the lack of a reciprocal social interface. Linked to this aspect is a greater need for educator preparation to be attentive in the guidance and training of this individual; that is, more and more, the academic training of the future educator must be based on seeing, understanding, comprehending and helping the other in the process of forming the self.

In the age of the internet and virtual interactions, in which the affective world has been reduced to numbers and visualizations on the net, an entire personality structure melts in the face of a few acts of action or interaction or the absence of it. The formation of any individual, to live and be able to act in the knowledge society, can no longer be thought of as something that happens only within the scope of the school. It is necessary to understand learning as a continuous activity, extending throughout life. The analysis of learning processes in different periods of life shows that learning as knowledge construction happens from childhood until the last moment of life.

Understood by experts and educators as essential and indispensable tools, new technologies gain effective space in classrooms. However, although many schools have these technologies, they are not used as they should, often being locked in isolated rooms and away from the handling of students and teachers. Does it matter now to say that students are connected to the network, via cell phone? What cannot be lost sight of is that the school is a training center; therefore, he must have control over what happens, because otherwise he cannot guide learning.

There are teachers and schools that still cannot link these instruments to their regular activities . Within this paradigm, the question arises whether the classroom can still be considered a privileged learning space in advanced societies where new communication and information technologies dominate?

Schools must create men capable of doing new things, and not simply repeating what other generations have done; train creative, inventive and discovering individuals, who do not accept everything that is proposed to them. For this, one must start with an education that makes learning pleasant and fun, without forgetting that the computer represents, throughout the educational process, a means and never an end in itself. It is not by chance that the introduction of new digital technologies in education brought changes to the social, cultural and technological dynamics. Pedagogical models were broken, becoming outdated in the face of new means of storing and disseminating information. At this time, the contents, values, competences, performances and abilities that are socially considered fundamental for human development also change .

So understood,

The role of education is to teach us to face life's uncertainty; it is to teach us what knowledge is, because they pass us knowledge. (...) In other words, the role of education is to instruct the spirit to live and face the difficulties of the world (MORIN, 2001, p. 05).

Contemporary educators are committed to building their students' social, personal and technological skills. They need to create conditions of knowledge, awareness and ability to think that face the challenges of life, ready to decide in a complex way, that is, thinking about their immediate and future interests, as well as collective and community interests. It is necessary that the teacher , in this new sociological perspective, be a partner of his students, stimulating their motivation to be autonomous, since this dialectic exchange and search for new knowledge is essential. Current technologies are vital for human development and help a lot in day-to-day practice; however, it is important that the educator is prepared and willing to provide both aspects of this change process.

Economic changes have caused changes in the way of life of every terrestrial community. And, in this new century, humanity has already woken up with the noise of brand new technologies that were not accompanied by work to consolidate and prepare the unfortunate souls that would be trampled by them. And the educational area was not unharmed by this impact.

The impact of New Technologies has caused changes in Education, which has not been slow to incorporate the latest technological resources aimed at the sector. In this way, the integration of new media such as television and the Internet is no longer a strange novelty in the classroom. On the contrary, it contributes to the creation of new teaching, learning and self-training strategies.

For Blikstein & Zufo (2010),

Many professions have been seduced, in recent years, by the enchanting melodies of new communication and information technologies. In the early 1990s, it was computer professionals, fascinated by the prospect of instant wealth and the undoubted aura of wisdom. Afterwards, it was the turn of electronic commerce and the “new economy”, which cradled the dreams of executives and administrators and promised the complete transformation of the business world. Later came the time of electronic journalism, elimination of paper, personalization of news, real-time delivery. Each one would receive only the news of interest, every morning, without having to search through pages and pages of paper. Informatics, e-commerce specialists and *web* -journalists, each in their own time, had their moment of glory, exposure, magical wisdom (Idem, 2010, p. 14).

But, since the school is a paradoxical environment, that is, it tends to form the human being to be and live as an autonomous, independent, free being, at the same time that it serves as an instrument of mass ideological inculcation, there is no doubt also on the importance of ongoing teacher training so that they use technological resources in a creative and innovative way. There is no point in having access to highly elaborate digital learning resources if they are used to reproduce traditional learning models. It is up to teachers to reflect on the best use of these resources with the aim of providing propitious situations for meaningful learning.

The great revolution that the computer promotes is to allow mass education in the sense that there is a lot of information available and at the same time individualized. As the years go by, what will happen is that teaching will no longer be reduced to the textbook. The books will be better and suitable for computing, even with suggestions for *sites* and activities. Lectures, paper, field research, laboratory work, consultations on the web are complementary resources that must be used in an integrated and intelligent way. Exactly the opposite of what is done in conventional education, which wastes the most precious of all resources... the teacher making him a mere provider of information, when he should be an organizer of learning situations (MOITA, 1992, *sp.*).

This placement seems a bit harsh and radical. The teacher is not wasted in the classroom. Nothing will replace the master's human contact with his students, the confidence he awakens in them, the praise, the criticism, the glimpses [*things that a computer outside of Hollywood will never be able to do*]. And, moreover, it is not enough to have the technology, it is necessary

to know how to use it, to take better advantage of it, when it comes to education . Creating a project is not enough; it is necessary to plan it to know the right moment to use it, developing it in its stages and using the technologies available. While the Public School does not have a state-of-the-art Video and Sound Laboratory, a Data Show Room and an enviable Computer Laboratory, do not remain a teacher in the Stone Age, as there are still many media that can be used to make classes more humane and dignified. But one should not forget that it is necessary to participate in training to demand and create means to qualify children's education.

When talking about technology, the idea that comes to mind is the computer. However, everything that is used to make the class different , richer, more pleasurable can be added to the title of technology value. Another aspect is that technology itself is not evil. The purposes for which they are used make them harmful and exclusive. Referring to the computer, this is just a machine, without a brain and without programmable feelings, and which depends on a human being behind it so that it can produce the miracles that are so attributed to it.

Technology, understood as one of the languages that man uses in terms of communication, is also a social construction which is realized and expanded historically, serving to transform socio-economic and cultural relations. According to Marx (1818-1883), technology reveals man's way of proceeding with nature, the immediate process of production of his material life and thus elucidates the conditions of his social life and the mental conceptions that result from it.

Macluhan claims that,

With the technology of literacy, Western man acquired the power to act without reaction. The advantages of fragmenting in this way can be exemplified by the case of the surgeon, who would become helpless if he had to become humanly involved in his interventions. We acquired the art of carrying out the most dangerous social operations with the most complete impartiality. Our exemption was an attitude of non-participation. But in the age of electricity, when our central nervous system is technologically designed to involve us in the whole of Humanity, incorporating it into us, we necessarily have to involve ourselves, in depth, in each of our actions. It is no longer possible to worship the Olympian and dissociated role of the Western literati (MCLUHAN , 1996, p. 18).

Searching for knowledge through these instrumental mediations, materialized in technologies, requires a form of collective work in the search for the unit-totally of knowledge, in pedagogical work. Contrary to what happens in capitalist production , where technique is only at the service of capital reproduction, technologies in pedagogical work must be at the service of non-competitiveness, but of solidary work, of an interdisciplinary collective practice with social quality, in the perspective of the transformation of society.

It is worth mentioning that understanding the binomial Education and Technology - means being clear that having the latest generation of certain technological artifacts in our hands is useless, but having the education professional as the main actor in the teaching-learning process. If he must be problematizing, mediating, inventive, transforming the scientific, historical and cultural knowledge produced by humanity, it must also be recognized that, among other needs, the training of this professional, who is an agent of change, become priorities so that the objectives education are properly achieved.

It is essential that the school, the teacher and the student are clear about the purposes or motives of the teaching and learning activity, contextualize their objectives, define the necessary actions and procedures to achieve these ends and consider the objects or available resources (technologies) for school work, starting from a critical analysis of reality, creating conditions for the formation of critical awareness committed to the transformation of society.

In education (and also in other sectors) this distinction is fundamental, as there is no machine that can replace the teacher – and when this occurs, it is because the teacher deserves it. Educational technology is, for example, using a can of water, a piece of wood and a stone to explain the fluctuation of bodies; pressing the button on a video on the subject and letting the students watch it passively, on the other hand, has nothing to do with technology .

When radar was new, there was a need to eliminate the balloon system that preceded radar as a city protection system. The balloons interfered with the electrical self-feeding of the new radar information. This seems to be the case with our current school curriculum, not to mention the arts in general. Either way, we should only use those manifestations that accentuate our perception of technology and its psychological and social consequences. Art, as a radar-environment, plays the role of indispensable perceptive training - and not of the role of a privileged diet for the elite. The purpose of art, as a radar-like self-feeder that provides us with a corporate, dynamic and changeable image, is not so much to prepare us for transformations as to allow us to maintain a stable roadmap towards permanent goals, even amid the most disturbing innovations. Well, we already realized the futility of changing our goals when we change our technologies” (MCLUHAN, 1996, p.15).

Mcluhan states with this speech that,

The “message” of any medium or technology is the change in scale, cadence or pattern that this medium or technology introduces into human things. The railroad did not introduce movement, transportation, wheels or paths into human society, but it accelerated and extended the scale of previous human functions, creating entirely new types of cities, work and leisure. This was regardless of whether the railroad was operating in a tropical or northern region, with no relation to the freight or contents of the rail vehicle. The plane, on the other hand, accelerating the pace of transport, tends to dissolve the

“railway” form of the city, politics and associations, regardless of the purpose for which it is used (MCLUHAN, 1996, p.22) .

With this, a new horizon can be glimpsed that points to the formation of a new educator. As much as we think about using video, the computer or even the good old blackboard, it is in teacher training that educational technology is developed, preparing leaders, mediators and stimulators, more than holders of certain knowledge. The teacher of this century must know how to guide students on where to gather information, how to treat that information, how to use the information obtained: *the how, why and what for* . This educator will guide self-training and advise students on learning, sometimes encouraging individual work, sometimes supporting the work of small groups gathered around areas of common interest.

ICT'S AND THE EDUCATIONAL CURRICULUM

In schools, what would be the most revolutionary use of technologies? The ones where students follow step-by-step recipes or when they undertake projects they are interested and passionate about, outside the strict regulations of conduct and behavior?

According to Del Nero, the oceanic availability of information is no guarantee of learning or building knowledge. It categorically states that

Research without direction, without a clear conceptual element that can digest and organize information, can create pseudocultures. [...] If this information is in enormous quantity and very fast, it is not too much to imagine that anxious pathologies arise , in addition to ignorance disguised as modernity, by exposure to diverse and poorly synthesized contexts (DEL NERO, 1997, p. 121).).

Rouanet (2002) also comments and criticizes the non-accidental confusion between information and knowledge society, reaffirming what Del Nero says about the need for internal work of reflection to transform information into knowledge. To ignore this difference, according to him, is to use these facts as an ideology in its most pernicious classical sense, that is, “a set of ideas to mystify real relations, in the service of a system of domination” (Idem, p. 02) .

There is, once again, a central problem: the advancement of technology has no counterpart in the daily lives of citizens and, among them, the teachers and students involved in the reality of the Public School, where a large part of the members of the school community do not have access to to new advances in technology. Note that we are not referring to television or radio, mass media that have long been part of Brazilian daily life.

What causes strangeness is to notice the creation of books and didactic material from sophisticated authoring *software* when most students and teachers do not have their own personal computer at home. The world can be connected via *the Internet* and many of the students leave school to face the job market before completing 1^o- Grade. A technique does not become a tool until you know how to handle it and apply creativity, imagination and knowledge to it. Technology, understood as one of the languages that man uses in terms of communication, is also a social construction which is realized and expanded historically, serving to transform socio-economic and cultural relations.

According to Marx (*apud* GAMA, 1986, p. 208), “technology reveals man's way of proceeding with nature, the immediate process of production of his material life and thus elucidates the conditions of his social life and mental conceptions. that follow from it.” In this sense, the development of scientific knowledge has contributed to putting a new basis on the way of thinking and producing technological innovations. In this sense, it is necessary to reflect on the ways of teaching and on the production of materials for an education committed to overcoming inequalities, conflicts and contradictions posed in society, without losing sight of cultural diversity. Searching for knowledge through these instrumental mediations, materialized in technologies, requires a form of collective work in the search for the unit-totality of knowledge, in pedagogical work. Contrary to what happens in capitalist production, where technique is only at the service of the reproduction of capital, technologies in pedagogical work must be at the service of non-competitiveness, but of solidary work, of an interdisciplinary collective practice with social quality, in perspective of the transformation of society.

According to Beppler *et all*,

Understanding the binomial Education and Technology means being clear that having the latest generation of certain technological artifacts in our hands is useless , but having the education professional as the main actor in the teaching-learning process. If he must be problematizing, mediating, inventive, transforming the scientific, historical and cultural knowledge produced by humanity, it must also be recognized that, among other needs, the training of this professional, who is an agent of change, become priorities so that the objectives education are duly achieved (2002, *sp*).

It is inferred from this author's statement that it is of no use having a professional who is very knowledgeable about all multimedia if he is unable to make the readings inherent to the scientific process that produced them and the possibilities that may arise from their correct application . Every living being resists the new. This is because the new is unknown and this provokes and enhances fear. And this is what is the cause of resistance. Even the development

of human culture and the species itself, had its obstacles, due to this fear, this resistance to accepting the unknown.

Any guidance that may be put forward for working with students, even if it eventually deals with specific aspects such as, for example, the use of video or computer, must be consistent with the concept already established for the set of Curriculum Proposal. According to this point of view, the mental activities determined by social relations imply the understanding that the process of knowledge appropriation occurs at the same time that the subjects develop themselves culturally . “The innovative process expresses man's ability to transform nature through work; technological change is the externalization of this potentiality” (KATZ, 1995, p. 09); although,

The term innovation is highly treacherous, being both seductive and misleading: seductive, because it implies improvement and progress, whereas in reality it just means something new and different. Misleading, because it diverts attention from the substance of the activity in question – learning – in favor of care for the technology of education (HUBERMAN, 1973, *sp* .).

Modern technologies came to add more value to the already complex system of human life, however, the way it was placed has caused real outbreaks of panic in people. Instead of being the guardian of transmitted learning, the teacher proposes the construction of knowledge by providing a field of possibilities, of paths that open up when elements are activated by learners. It guarantees the possibility of free and plural meanings, and, without losing sight of consistency with its critical option embedded in the proposition, it makes itself open to expansions, to modifications coming from the learners.

Technologies arrived at school, but they always favored control, infrastructure modernization and management more than change. Administrative management programs are more developed than those geared towards learning. There are advances in the virtualization of learning, but they can only scratch the surface of the heavy structure in which the various levels of education are structured.

Despite institutional resistance, pressures for change are growing stronger. Companies are very active in *online education* and look to universities for more agility, flexibility and speed in offering continuing education. The advances in distance education with the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LEI 9394/1996) and the *Internet* are being remarkable. The *LDB* legalized distance education and the *Internet* took away the air of isolation, backwardness, of second- class teaching. The interconnectivity that the *Internet* and networks have developed in recent years is starting to revolutionize the way we teach and learn.

Face-to-face education is incorporating technologies, functions, activities that were typical of distance education, and distance learning is discovering that it can teach in a less individual way, maintaining a balance between flexibility and interaction.

With conventional teaching processes and the current dispersion of attention in urban life, autonomy and personal organization, which are indispensable for distance learning processes, are very difficult. The disorganized student may miss the appropriate time for each activity, discussion, production and may find it difficult to keep up with the pace of a course. This will get in the way of your motivation, your own learning and that of the group, which will create tension or indifference. Students like this, little by little, may stop participating, producing and many will find it difficult, from a distance, to regain motivation, enthusiasm for the course. In face-to-face classes, a conversation with close colleagues or the professor can help those who want to participate in the course again. From a distance it will be possible, but not easy. Teachers are increasingly aware of the gap in the field of technology and, in general, try to hold back as much as they can, making small concessions, without changing the essentials. Many teachers are afraid to reveal their difficulty in front of the student. Because of this and through habit, they maintain a repressive, controlling, repeating structure. Teachers realize they need to change, but they don't quite know how to do it and aren't prepared to experiment safely. Many institutions also demand changes from professors without giving them the conditions to do so. Often some organizations introduce computers, connect schools with the Internet and hope that this alone will improve teaching problems. Administrators are frustrated that so much effort and money tied up does not translate into significant changes in classes and faculty attitudes.

It is difficult to maintain motivation in face-to-face sessions, much more so in virtual settings, if you do not involve students in participative, affective processes that inspire confidence. Courses that are limited to the transmission of information, content, even if they are brilliantly produced, run the risk of long-term demotivation and, above all, that learning is only theoretical, insufficient to account for the theory/practice relationship. In the classroom, if you are attentive, you can more easily get *feedback* on the problems that occur and try to dialogue or find new pedagogical strategies. In the virtual one, the student is more distant, usually only accessible by e-mail, which is cold, not immediate, or by an occasional phone call, which, although more direct, in a distance course increases the final cost.

Outstanding educators are not only attractive for their ideas, but also for their personal contact. They convey kindness and competence, both on a personal, family and social level, inside and outside the classroom, face-to-face or virtual. There is always something surprising,

different in what they say, in the relationships they establish, in the way they look, the way they communicate, the way they act. And they, in an increasingly complex and virtual society, will become necessary references.

Even with state-of-the-art technologies, there are still great difficulties in emotional management, both personal and organizational, which makes quick learning difficult. Changes in education depend, more than on new technologies, on having educators, managers and students who are intellectually, emotionally and ethically mature; curious, enthusiastic, open people who know how to motivate and dialogue; people with whom it is worthwhile to come into contact, because they leave it enriched. There are few educators who integrate theory and practice and bring thinking and living closer together.

CONCLUSION

Computers are amazing machines; but not enough to replace human beings in their social functions. The impression remains that the machines will rebel and leave everyone at the mercy of luck and misfortune, and that all of nature will bow to the creation of a species that is too limited. There is an inferiority complex masked under a superiority complex. One cannot deny the advances produced through the media; but under no circumstances can anthropophobia lead human beings to bend their spines to such an extent that they become an eternal hunchback, never able to look their peers in the eye again.

Understanding the process of media technological revolution permeates the domain of the subject's own self as supposed knowledge and as subject of the educational process. Ignorance is a lesser evil than supposed wisdom. Schopenhauer (1788-1860) spoke of a book culture, today one can speak of a media culture. At the time of the philosopher, this was a type of culture of people who only repeated what was written in the records; they read, but did not mull over what they had ingested, to paraphrase Nietzsche. Nowadays, they only listen, they don't even know how to read anymore, they don't even dominate the native language and call themselves intellectuals. To the educator, in this new paradigm, it is up to conduct this process in the midst of the views to lead the subject to discover himself; always assuming a stance that promotes debate and interaction between peers and scientific knowledge.

Technology makes direct access to information possible, but direct access to knowledge is not possible. Moving from an intuitive and summary knowledge of common sense to a - reflective development in which the individual is able to organize, associate and establish

relationships with information is not achieved with the immediacy of the direct: it requires time, calm and patience to learn to think and from there learn to learn.

Pedagogical knowledge consists of a set of empirical, theoretical knowledge and the result of practical activities that teachers acquire in their initial and continuous training, and which is materialized in the formulation of specific curricular and pedagogical projects for a given educational level, programs, methods and strategies education. Therefore, pedagogical knowledge, despite its scientific foundation and axiological and social legitimacy, depend on a context of action that requires constant updates and adaptations.

For more than two decades in Brazil, information technology has been discussed in public schools. Initiatives have emerged to offer computers to teachers and students in schools and to prepare teachers in the didactic use of new technologies. However, there are few public school educators who actually consider the computer lab, when available in these institutions, a space for teaching and learning.

Training courses or access to technology itself can help teachers to see themselves as more adept at using the computer and more prepared to teach with technology, consequently also contributing, according to the study data, to the construction of a concept of effectiveness and/or formation of a digital autonomy. The motivation to teach with technology requires rethinking the teaching work conditions, whether in relation to the available infrastructure or the time the teacher has to prepare classes or participate in training courses. However, when thinking about a training course, it is important to consider who this teacher is, how long he has been trained and teaching experience, and what skills he believes he has when using the computer, to the point of evaluating the what needs to be done to help you make effective use of available technology resources.

What is finally concluded is that the technological and mediatic means brought about revolutions and these entered the school space as a way to improve the technical knowledge of the students and reduce barriers that before could even be imagined that would be overcome from a click of a button. There are many opportunities for teachers to carry out in-depth work based on their possibilities and using their students' knowledge and mastery of information technology and its resources.

It starts with a contextualization to refer that information and communication technologies can help a lot so that the pedagogical praxis in all areas can be reinvented and improved in its most dynamic and scientific aspect, contributing greatly to the production of new interpretations about the world that surrounds the student and in which he lives.

REFERENCES

- BEPLLER, Adalberto Matias. *Technology in a Historical-Cultural Perspective*. São Paulo: Electronic Magazine 'Curricular Proposal', 2002.
- BLIKSTEIN, Paulo; ZUFFO Marcelo Knörich. *The Sirens of E-Learning*. São Paulo: Edusp, 2010.
- BRAZIL. *Federal Constitution of 1988*. Federative Republic of Brazil. Brasilia. Federal Senate Graphic Center, 1998. (Art. 205).
- DEL NERO, Henrique Schültzer. *The site of the mind: thought, emotion and will in the human brain*. São Paulo: Collegium cognitio, 1997.
- GAMA, Ruy. *Technology and work in history*. São Paulo: Nobel Bookstore SA, 1986.
- GOMES, Morgana. *The Life and Work of Charles Chaplin*. São Paulo: Escala, 2007.
- HUBERMAN, AM *How changes are made in education . Subsidies for the study of the problem of innovation*. Culture, Sao Paulo, 1973.
- KATZ, Claudio. *Neoliberalism or crisis of capital?* São Paulo: Xamã, 1995.
- KATZENSTEIN, Ursula. *The Origin of the Book from the Stone Age to the advent of letterpress printing in the West*. So Paulo: Hucitec, 1986.
- MCLUHAN, Marshall. *The Media as Extensions of Man*. São Paulo: Cultrix, 1996.
- MILGRAM, Stanley. *Obedience to Authority*. Rio de Janeiro: Francisco Alves, 1983.
- MOITA, Maria da Conceicao. Training and trans-training paths. In: NÓVOA, António (Org.). *Teachers' Lives*. Portugal: Porto, 1992.
- MORIN, Edgar. *The Ethical Challenges of Development*. Faculty of Economic Sciences of the University of Buenos Aires. Buenos Aires, ARGENTINA, September 5th and 6th, 2001.
- NIETZSCHE, F. *Writings on Education*. São Paulo: Loyola, 2003.
- ROUANET, SP *Fact, ideology, utopia*. Caderno Mais - Folha de São Paulo, 03/24/2002.
- SETZER, Valdemar. Lecture given at the Distance Education Center of the Federal University of Juiz de Fora - MG, 2013.